

Development Of Sewing Board Media To Optimize The Fine Motor Abilities Of Cerebral Palsy Students (CP)

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Abstract

These children with special needs generally have differences both physically, mentally and socially, emotionally. They require adjustments in the learning process. The adjustment is made in order to optimize their development like other children. various types of children with special needs, one of which is children who do not have physical abilities (disabled). Disability can be classified into two types, namely disorders of the function of the orthopedic limb (orthopedic disability) and disorders of the function of the limb of the nerve (neurological disability). Cerebral Palsy (CP) is a part of neurological disabilities (physical disabilities), they also do not escape the attention and reach of educational services. The purpose of this study was to optimize the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students at TKLB SLB D YPAC, South Jakarta. The development of the learning model used in this study is the ADDIE Approach (Analysis-Design-Develop-Implement-Evaluate) Learning Design Model which is strengthened by the results of the instrument validity and reliability test data. The results of presenting data are in the form of analysis results and facts that the researchers found in the field, and adjusted to the theory used in this study. The discussion on the presentation of the data is the result of analysis and facts that the researchers found in the field, and has been adjusted to the theory used in this study so that it can optimize the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students at TKLB SLB D YPAC, South Jakarta through sewing board media. . After doing research and development on the sewing board media, the sewing board media that has been developed has proven to be effective and can be used in optimizing the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students.

I. INTRODUCTION

The differences in each child's development will vary, knowing and understanding the developmental phases of a child can certainly help an educator optimize the learning that will be given, especially if this learning is aimed at children with special needs. These children with special needs generally have differences both physically, mentally and socially, emotionally. They have special characteristics that result in adjustments in various fields so that they continue to have the same rights as other children. The adjustment is made in order to optimize their development like other children. These adjustments can be in the form of: a learning environment that can accommodate the needs of all children, adjustment of children's academic abilities, skills and knowledge of educators in order to understand the child's condition, adjustment of learning activities, adjustment of learning facilities and infrastructure, adjustment with peers and adjustment to the community environment.

(Efendi, 2009) states that there are various types of children with special needs, one of which is children who do not have physical abilities (disabled). Disability can be classified into two types, namely disorders of the function of the orthopedic limb (orthopedic disability) and disorders of the function of the limb of the nerve (neurological disability). Orthopedic disability is a child who experiences disability, disability, and certain imperfections in his motoric body, especially in the bones, body muscles and joint areas, for example: Poliomyelitis, Bone Tuberculosis, Osteomyelitis and Arthritis. Meanwhile, neurological disabilities are abnormalities in the function of the limbs (motor disorders of the hands or feet) caused by disorders of the nervous system. One of the people with neurological disabilities can be seen in children with Cerebral Palsy (CP), which shows that physical disabilities can be classified into two types, namely disorders of the function of orthopedic limbs (orthopedic disabilities) and disorders of the function of nervous limbs (neurological disabilities). while orthopedic disabilities are children who experience disabilities, disabilities, and certain imperfections in their motoric bodies, especially in the bones, muscles of the body and in the joints. For Cerebral Palsy (CP), there is an obstacle to the nervous system in the brain during growth and development.

(Salim, 2000) argues that Cerebral Palsy (CP) is a part of neurological disabilities (physical disabilities), they also do not escape the attention and reach of educational services. This is fully realized by educators who are experts in the field of Special Education because when viewed from their existence, this child with Cerebral Palsy (CP) will remain throughout human life, and the general public has not seen that children with special needs, including children with Cerebral Palsy (CP) still has the potential that can be developed optimally so that they can live independently and do not have to burden others.

The disruption of motor function experienced by children with Cerebral Palsy (CP) will result in impaired movement and posture, mobility and motor limitations so that various difficulties will arise that affect their learning outcomes, such as: intellectual disorders, seizure disorders, communication difficulties, behavior and independence in activities. daily. The emergence of this difficulty requires efforts to improve, shape and strengthen their fine motor skills so that Cerebral Palsy (CP) students can carry out a motion correctly with guidance in the form of stimulation towards the development of motion so that it can produce meaningful movements for Cerebral Palsy (CP) students.).

The results of observations in the class concluded that the teacher always tries to provide assistance to optimize the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students in TKLB classes by using guidance on children's physical abilities by using simple activities that aim to strengthen joint muscles so that children's physical abilities will be more flexible and less stiff. Things to do, such as: 1). Strengthening the muscles through physiotherapy, occupational therapy, playing therapy and music therapy with the aim of keeping joint motion from being too stiff, 2). Improving joint movements through simple playing activities such as catching the ball, playing using various light tools such as small balls and large balls, moving water using sponges, doing light exercise can help maintain the fitness of children with Cerebral Palsy, 3). Positioning and posture such as directing the child to sit properly using an upright body position, not bending over and striving for the head to be straight, not down. This movement building activity is carried out through playing using various educational game tools (APE) to train fine motor skills, eight of which are: playing with playdough, playing with a smile, playing with a small ball, catching the ball, matching colors using color puzzles, painting using paint. water, finger painting uses watercolor and has used a sewing board media even though the results are not in accordance with expectations because the child is only limited to working and does not understand the concept of front and back when sewing on a sewing board and sewing board is there and has been used it turns out to be difficult for children, especially for children Cerebral Palsy (CP).

This fact makes researchers assume that the existing and used sewing board media is not a product of the result of Research because if it is assessed in terms of suitability, the sewing board media cannot be said to be in accordance with the conditions and needs of children with special needs, especially for Cerebral Palsy (CP) students.). This is because reviewing the sewing board media used in the classroom has the following criteria: a). Has a distance between holes that are close to each other, which is about 2 cm, b). There is a small hole size of about 4 mm, c). The number of holes varies between 10 holes to 30 holes making it difficult for Cerebral Palsy (CP) students, especially for Cerebral Palsy (CP) students of the Spastic Quadriplegia type (paralysis of the limbs in the form of two paralyzed hands and two legs) and Cerebral Palsy students (CP) with Low Vision resistance to insert the rope into the hole and pull the rope back out of the hole on the sewing board. In general, Cerebral Palsy (CP) students when playing the sewing board did not finish it because it was not interesting, bored and considered difficult.

The reason the researchers chose the sewing board media with the aim of being able to provide activities for fine motoric movements that would be assembled according to the learning theme so that students became more interested so that they could optimize the ability of movement for Cerebral Palsy (CP) students by involving the coordination of the hands and eyes. and brains. The research objectives are: 1). Knowing the sewing board media model that will be used in order to optimize the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students so far, 2). Knowing the development of the sewing board media in order to optimize the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students, 3). Knowing the steps for using sewing board media to optimize the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students, 4). Knowing the effectiveness of the sewing board media to optimize the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students, 5). Knowing the purpose of providing sewing board media for students with special needs, especially for Cerebral Palsy (CP) students at TKLB SLB D YPAC, South Jakarta.

THEORITICAL STUDY

1. Fine Motoric In Early Childhood

a. Motor Skills in Early Childhood

(Diane Trister Dodge, 1999) states that physical development is sometimes taken for granted in early education. There is an assumption that children will develop through a predictable sequence of stages and acquire predictable skills. However, in some ways what is true, a number of factors can promote or slow down physical development. Normal physical development depends on good health, proper nutrition and a safe environment. Proper nutrition begins during pregnancy which is very important for mental and physical development and during these years children will need balanced meals and snacks that are high in nutrients and

low in fat, sugar salt. In line with healthy nutrition, when young children will grow physically, their muscles grow and become strong.

(Ungerleider, Doyon, & Karni, 2002) revealed that motor development is the development of elements of maturity and control of body movements which are closely related to the development of motor centers in the brain. In everyday life, we carry out activities using various motor skills that are acquired gradually through practice and interaction with our environment.

(Formiga & Linhares, 2015) states that motor can be defined as the whole process that occurs in the human body, which includes the control process (coordination) and the regulatory process (physical condition) which is influenced by physiological factors and psychological factors to get a good movement. Motor functions as a motor that is contained in the human body. Motor and movement are not the same, but they are related. Related to this, fine motor skills can be said to be movements performed by certain body parts and only involve a small portion of the body's muscles. This movement does not require strength, but it needs coordination between the eyes and hands. Fine motor movement is the result of training and learning by paying attention to the maturity of motor organ functions.

b. Motor Skills in Early Childhood with Cerebral Palsy (CP)

(BandiDelphie, 2010) states that motoric physical condition is a condition of a person's physical inability to move due to abnormalities that occur due to neurological disorders, muscle and bone condition problems, congenital defects, due to accidents and other conditions. Children with physical motor impairments have difficulty in terms of perception and level of mobility. Hendaya physical condition lies in the difficulty of movement, difficulty in perception and postural disorders, especially for children with Cerebral Palsy (CP). In general, the obstacles lie in: 1). Inability to orient space, 2). Movement coordination disorders due to physical motor weakness, 3). Generally, the inability to adapt is due to too much pressure from the environment during social interactions (psychological aspects), 4). Inability to solve simple problems.

(Sense & Development, 2017) reveals the problems that arise when a child with Cerebral Palsy (CP) experiences fine motor problems 1). Behavior in which they can avoid or refuse to participate in fine motor tasks, 2). Frustrated with proper eye and hand coordination tasks, 3) Avoiding these tasks and choosing other people to do fine motor-related tasks, 4). Demonstrate academic ability: be skilled orally but have difficulty demonstrating writing skills on paper (eg writing, drawing and sticking), 5). Academic performance: the obstacles a child has when completing an academic task.

2. Children Cerebral Palsy (CP)

(Klingels et al., 2011) stated that children with Cerebral Palsy (CP) showed motor impairment, quality of movement and involvement of hands in bimanual tasks that did not improve spontaneously over one year, except for related changes in age and strength. like grasping. However, it appears that children with unilateral Cerebral Palsy (CP), particularly children with high proficiency levels and children with congenital lesions, can learn more adaptive movement strategies, resulting in improvements in fine motor skills.

(Singer, Mink, Gilbert, & Jankovic, 2016) stated that Cerebral Palsy (CP) is stiffness located in the brain. The etiology of Cerebral Palsy (CP) ranges from prenatal and perinatal events to postnatal insults. Hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) represents only a small category in neonatal encephalopathy and is an even smaller contributor to the cause of Cerebral Palsy (CP). The causes of non-hypoxic or asphyxiated Cerebral Palsy (CP) are many and include cerebral dysgenesis, intrauterine infection, intrauterine growth restriction, preterm birth, coagulation disorders, antepartum hemorrhage, multiple pregnancy, abnormal presentation, neurometabolic disease, chromosomal anomalies, selected polymorphisms, congenital abnormalities and many others that affect mother or child. Neonatal stroke (ischemic perinatal infarction or synovena thrombosis) is an important cause of Cerebral Palsy (CP).

(Jamaris, 2010) states, Cerebral Palsy (CP) is the most common form of physical abnormalities. This condition is not caused by disease but is caused by a static brain malfunction that causes paralysis and movement disorders.

(Friend, 2005) states the same thing that Cerebral Palsy (CP) literally means brain paralysis. This is a group of conditions that involve non-progressive control of muscles, posture, and movements, that is, they don't get worse. The problem that occurs in students with Cerebral Palsy (CP) is not in the muscles themselves.

Cerebral Palsy (CP) is a movement and posture disorder caused by damage to the motor control center of the brain. This condition is not caused by disease but is caused by a static brain malfunction that causes paralysis and movement disorders. which can occur before birth, during the birth process, after birth due to an accident or injury. The impact that occurs is that generally they will have difficulty moving parts of the body or the whole body, speaking and communicating non-verbally (facial expressions may not always reveal real emotions), involuntary muscle movements (seizures) or otherwise lacking reflexes to reactions, eating and drinking is disturbed because of muscle stiffness or too flexible, muscle weakness, including the muscles needed in the process of breathing so that it is often tight, lack of balance and coordination, lack of attention and concentration.

3. Use of Media in the Learning Process

(JalinusNizwardi, 2016) states media is in the plural form of the word Medium and is a word that comes from the Latin Medius which literally means middle, intermediary or introduction. Therefore the media can be interpreted as an intermediary for messages from the sender to the recipient of the message and the media as a vehicle for channeling learning information or transmitting messages.

(Azwardi, 2009) states that the word educational media is often used interchangeably with the term aids or communication media where the communication relationship will run smoothly with maximum results when using a tool called communication media.

(Chotimah, Chusnul, Fathurrohman, 2018) stated that the media is a container for messages that the message source or channel wants to be forwarded to the target or recipient of the message.

Media as an intermediary for messages from sender to recipient of messages, media as all forms and channels used by people to transmit messages or information. Media can be used as a learning aid that can be used to convey the content of teaching material from learning sources to students so that it can stimulate interest, attention, thoughts and feelings so that the learning process becomes more effective and can improve learning outcomes.

RESEARCH METHODS

The development of the learning model used in this study is the ADDIE Approach (Analysis-Design-Develop-Implement-Evaluate) Learning Design Model. The ADDIE Approach can be developed systematically and is based on the theoretical foundation of learning design. This model is arranged programmatically with a systematic sequence of activities in an effort to solve learning problems related to learning resources that are in accordance with the needs and characteristics of students. Through the ADDIE model, there is an opportunity to evaluate the development activities of each stage.

The evaluation technique used is a non-test evaluation technique. In this research and development, researchers used questionnaire and observation techniques. The evaluation technique by distributing closed and open questionnaires was carried out through expert reviews and evaluation techniques in the form of observations carried out during field trials to Cerebral Palsy (CP) students using a sewing board media. Expert reviews and field trials were conducted by means of one to one evaluation.

Instrument Validity Test Results

The validity test is carried out to measure the high level of accuracy and consistency of the research instruments that have been used in data collection. To find the validity value of an item, the correlation between the item score and the item's total score is used.

The validity test was carried out to test each item of the question in the questionnaire instrument used. The validity test was conducted to test the validity of each question item in the questionnaire instrument used. The test is said to be valid if the Corrected Item Total Correlation value which is the count of each question item must be greater than the rtabel value.

Instrument Reliability Test Results

The reliability test is carried out to determine whether the measurements that have been carried out produce consistent or stable answers over time. That is, the consistency of measuring instruments in producing data is called constant if the data measured by the same tool and repeatedly produce relatively the same data. The decision is made by looking at the value of Cronbach's Alpha.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Recapitulation of comparison of pre test, post test and effectiveness of fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students.

To determine the comparison of the pre test, post test and the effectiveness of the sewing board media to optimize the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students, the authors used 4 (four) dimensions, namely the dimensions of hand motion flexibility, hand eye coordination, accuracy and speed.

Table 4.1

The Average Value Of The Recapitulation Of The Effectiveness Of The Pre Test, Post Test And The Effectiveness Of The Sewing Board Media To Optimize The Fine Motor Skills Of Cerebral Palsy (CP) Students

No	Indicator	Pre Test		Post test		Efektivitas	
		Mean	%	Mean	%	Mean	%
A	Flexibility of Hand Movements						
1	The child is able to reach the sewing board using five fingers	2.25	56.25	3.58	89.58	3.83	95.75

2	The child is able to hold the sewing board using five fingers	2.25	56.25	3.25	81.25	3.50	87.50
	Average	2.25	56.25	3.42	85.42	3.67	91.63
B	Hand Eye Coordination						
3	Able to carry out sewing tasks in accordance with directions	2.50	62.50	3.50	87.50	3.88	96.88
4	Able to control hand movements while working on sewing tasks,	2.50	62.50	3.55	88.75	3.78	94.50
5	Able to concentrate while working on sewing tasks	2.75	68.75	3.63	90.75	3.50	87.50
	Average	2.58	64.58	3.56	89.00	3.72	92.96
C	Accuracy						
6	Able to insert the rope into the sewing board holes according to the directions	2.50	62.50	3.48	87.00	4.00	100.00
7	Be able to use thumb and index finger to pull the string out of the sewing board hole	2.75	68.75	3.55	88.75	4.00	100.00
8	Able to exert fingers to do sewing tasks until all holes on the sewing board are covered with string	3.00	75.00	3.50	87.50	3.80	95.00
9	Able to sew following the holes on the sewing board	2.00	50.00	3.40	85.00	3.25	81.25
	Average	2.56	64.06	3.48	87.06	3.76	94.06
D	Speed						
10	Be able to use hands to properly thread the string into the sewing board hole	2.50	62.50	3.48	87.00	3.83	95.75
11	Be able to use your hands to quickly pull out the string from the sewing board hole	2.25	56.25	3.55	88.75	4.00	100.00
12	Able to use hands to complete sewing tasks as directed	3.00	75.00	3.55	88.75	4.00	100.00
13	Able to show enthusiasm so that sewing tasks can be completed completely	3.00	75.00	3.63	90.75	4.00	100.00
14	Able to show the desire to change to a different picture pattern when it's finished	3.00	75.00	3.83	95.75	4.00	100.00
	Average	2.75	68.75	3.61	90.20	3.97	99.15
	Mean All	2.54		3.52		3.78	
	Score Percentage	63.41		87.92		94.45	

The recapitulation results of the effectiveness of the pre test, post test and the effectiveness of the sewing board media to optimize the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students are described as follows:

In the dimensions of flexibility in hand movements, the fine motor skills of each child with Cerebral Palsy (CP) have increased after using a sewing board design. This means that when using the sewing board media, each student's flexibility in hand movements does not experience progress, but after using the sewing board design each student has developed. Thus the sewing machine board design is very effective in the flexibility dimensions of hand motion.

Fine Motor Skills for Cerebral Palsy Students

Based on table 4.1 regarding the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy students in the pre test using a sewing board with an average value of 2.54 (63.38%), which means that the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) children develop quite optimally after using sewing board media. In the posttest using the sewing board design, the average value of the speed dimensions increased to 3.52 (87.94%), which means that the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) children for the dimension of speed develop very optimally after using the sewing board media. The effective test of the sewing board design is 94.50%, this means that the sewing machine board design is very effective for improving the fine motor skills of children with Cerebral Palsy (CP).

The following is a comparison of the pre test using a sewing board and the post test using a sewing board design

Tabel 4.2
Comparison of Pre Test and Post Test

No	Dimensions	Pre-Test	Post-Test	Efektivitas
1	Flexibility of hand movements	Obtain a percentage of 56.25% which means that the fine motor skills of children with Cerebral Palsy (CP) did not develop at all after using the sewing board media.	Experienced an increase in the score to 85.42%, which means that the fine motor skills of children with Cerebral Palsy (CP) develop very optimally after using sewing board media	The score increased to 95.72%, which means that the fine motor skills of children with Cerebral Palsy (CP) develop optimally after using a sewing board media.
2	Hand Eye Coordination	Getting a percentage of 64.58% which means that the fine motor skills of children with Cerebral Palsy (CP) develop quite optimally after using the sewing board media.	Experiencing an increase in the score to 89.00%, which means that the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) children develop optimally after using the sewing board media.	Experienced an increase in the score to 92.96% which means that the fine motor skills of children with Cerebral Palsy (CP) develop very optimally after using a sewing board media.
3	Accuracy	Obtained a percentage of 64.06% which means that the fine motor skills of children	Experienced an increase in the score to 87.06%, which means that the	Experienced an increase in the score to 87.50% which means that the

		with Cerebral Palsy (CP) develop quite optimally after using the sewing board media.	fine motor skills of children with Cerebral Palsy (CP) develop very optimally after using sewing board media.	fine motor skills of children with Cerebral Palsy (CP) develop very optimally after using sewing board media.
4	Speed	Getting a percentage of 68.75% which means that the fine motor skills of children with Cerebral Palsy (CP) develop quite optimally after using board media.	Experience an increase in score to 89.53% which means that the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) children develop optimally after using sewing board media.	Experienced an increase in the score to 94.06% which means that the fine motor skills of children with Cerebral Palsy (CP) develop very optimally after using sewing board media.

The discussion on the presentation of the data above is the result of analysis and facts that the researchers found in the field, and has been adjusted to the theory used in this study so that it can optimize the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students at TKLB SLB D YPAC, South Jakarta through the media. sewing board.

CONCLUSION

After doing research and development on the sewing board media, the following are the conclusions that can be given, namely:

1. The sewing board media model used for Cerebral Palsy (CP) students at SLB D YPAC, South Jakarta includes the shape and size of the sewing board and the drawing model has been adjusted to the learning theme and changes according to the theme accompanied by a background with a choice of colors
2. The sewing board has used a puzzle-like design that is adapted to the learning theme and aims to train eye-hand coordination so that students are expected to concentrate on putting back the sewing board according to the available home patterns.
3. The steps for using the sewing board media to optimize the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students at SLB D YPAC, South Jakarta have been written briefly on the back of the sewing board so that students with other special needs can use them according to instructions.
4. The sewing board media is very effective in improving the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students at SLB D YPAC, South Jakarta. This is evidenced by the results of the effectiveness test which involves four dimensions, namely: flexibility of hand movements, hand eye coordination, accuracy and speed.
5. The purpose of providing sewing board media for students with special needs, especially for Cerebral Palsy (CP) students at SLB D YPAC, South Jakarta is to optimize the fine motor skills of Cerebral Palsy (CP) students so that adjustments to the sewing board media are needed. given and attempted to comply with the needs and conditions of Cerebral Palsy (CP).

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